

**Archaeological monuments of Usturt of the early Middle Ages
(V-XI century)**

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Annotation: There are sources from the early Middle Ages about the region of Usturt bordering the Khorezm oasis. Among them, Ibn Ruste, Al Istahri (IX-X), Ibn Fadlan (922), Al Muqaddasi (985), Ibn Battuta (1333), A. Jenkinson (1558) and scholars of the new era we learned in his works.

Ibn Fadlan (921-922 years) in his "Treatise" on the road from Jurjan (Urganch) on the side of Usturt, "bab at Turk" (Zamdjan-Shemaha shahar), and then Git-Jit (Pulijoy) are converted into early medieval settlements. . The distance between them is given as a farsah (5.6 km). 1 The caravan that Ibn Fadlan left from the Usturt steppe traveled for 10 years to the Eastern Caspian.

According to Al-Maqdisi (10th century), among the cooperation of the people of Khorezim in trade relations with the outside world, Khorezim and Bulgaria and other countries and cities along the Volga in Eastern Europe are mentioned. For example, Al Maqdisi writes that beavers, white martens, rabbit furs, khaki, bow arrows, hats, fish, walrus teeth, daggers, savuts, and Slavic slaves, black cattle are brought from Bulgaria to Khorezm [1. 137].

Khorezim produced large cattle breeding products and royal armor. From the examples given, we can see that the cities and peoples of the Southern Island

were in cultural contact with the East and most of the related countries through Usturt in the 9th-10th centuries [1. 139].

Another Arab geographer Al Khomawi (1219-1220 years) tells about the cities among the information about the history of Khorezm that he saw with his own eyes. In his work, he writes about Urganch (al Jurjaniya), Khaivak (Khiva), Zamakhshar, Baf, Ishsha, Tumurtash, Harur, Hushmisan, Ruzan and Dorgon. Al-Hamawi's information about Subrna helps to identify the border areas of Khorezm on the Iranian side. S.P. Tolstov compares Subra with the Shah monument [1. 142].

Al-Hamawi's information about Subrna helps to identify the border areas of Khorezm on the Iranian side. S.P. Tolstov compares Subra with the monument of Shah. But it is worth saying that Al Hamawi rarely remembers the monument of Ustur near Khorezm. The great traveler Ibn Battuta (1333) also wrote about the trade route through Usturt in Eastern Europe in his work "Travel" [2. 179].

The connections of Khorezm with Usturt to Eastern Europe, the use of iron weapons in military work, and the local conditions of trade are also recorded in the sources of the late feudalism period. For example, Antony Jenkenson, an agent of the "Moscow-London" trade firm, visited Usturt in 1555, that is, Dav Kesken (Selluser) in Khorezm, and recalled that local blacksmiths made bows and arrows in the traditional way.

Excerpts from the works of the authors cited by us are well known to the scientific community, and the information presented in them is partially used in scientific publications. However, this source information has not been deeply studied, especially the history of material culture during the time of Usturt and Khorezmshahs. In fact, comparing the information of the works of the mentioned authors with the sources of archaeological research will undoubtedly lead to positive conclusions [2. 180].

In general, in the science of archeology, the location of the cities of Usturt and Khorezm, which were mentioned in the Middle Ages, and the ruins of which have reached our days, is the solution to the problem of solving the problem of

which monument has reached our days, in the work of Y.G. Gulomov “The Water Supply History of Khorezim”. The issues that need to be resolved from the beginning of the period are clarified. During the time of the scientist “Great Khorezimshahs”, cultural life and trade relations flourished in the outskirts of Khorezm, starting from Tekesh, the expansion of urban development zones (towards Usturt and the “Shahristan Road”), as a result of the political and cultural rise in the XI-XIII centuries, is not only in the history of the oasis “in the Muslim East”. Also notes that it was not observed in the Middle Ages [2. 181].

In general, the results of academician Y. G'. Gulomov's excellent work with the sources of history, archeology, ethnography, oriental studies, the monuments located near the mountains of Usturt (Tuproq Castle, Bugrakhan, Puljoy) are applied in the study of many areas of the history of Khorezm [3].

In 1937, under the auspices of the Institute of Ethnography of the Russian Academy of Sciences, the Khorezm archaeological-ethnographic expedition led by S.P. Tolstov went abroad in Moscow. This expedition stopped the archaeological and ethnographic research in the Khorezm oasis only after the allied republics disintegrated and disintegrated, but realized their identity and embarked on the path of their own development. However, over the course of several decades, the expedition members discovered the monuments of Khorezm civilization from the Stone Age to the late Middle Ages [4. 167].

These researches made a new contribution to the study of Khorezm's trade centers and its relations with Western feudal states. Among the many books, there are information about trade relations written by the expedition staff about Usturt. Among the members of the expedition, S.P. Tolstov, N.N. Vakturskaya, E.E. Nerazik, Yu.A. Rapopotlar studied and wrote several of their works in connection with the monuments of Usturt (Shemakhal Castle, Katta Aybuyur), cultural aspect and trade relations. This made it possible to study the history of Khorezm's trade relations with the Western peoples from all sides and to publish books with practical features. In particular, in the articles and books published by them, they serve as guides to the researches of young scientists. They helped in writing the

history of some nations. Therefore, we cannot stop separately on the researches of the above-mentioned scientists [5. 145].

In 1946-1947, S.P. Tolstov carried out inspections along the air and car roads along the Usturt road. During these researches, along with medieval city fortifications, Buloq, Uchquduq, Kosbuloq, Kichik Aybuyur, caravan-palaces and guard mounds were studied [3. 415].

In general, S.P. Tolstov, one of the major representatives of Central Asian archeology, the organizer of the Khorezm archaeological expedition, along with other field diggers, organizes the inspection of the archaeological monuments of the Middle Ages, the Khorezmshahs-Anushtegins, and the Golden Horde period in Usturt. In Usturt, in the Amudarya basin, the castles on the endless roads, along the old irrigation ditches, towns and caravans-palaces on the trade route in Usturt, and many of the memorial monuments proved that they were built by the kingdom of Khorezm state in several centuries. For example, in the fundamental work “Ancient Khorezm”, the empire of the Khorezm Shahs is assessed as follows; “In the face of its destruction, this powerful state in the Middle and Middle East, this empire that was hit by the Mongols, the destruction of their honor was subjected to the first pressure of the movement, thus, in gratitude to Russia, he served to save Western European civilization” [6. 178].

Ilik did great work in the archeology of Karakalpak during the study of medieval Khorazim dynasty in Usturt, during the research of medieval fortresses, and during the study of trade. The establishment of the Karakalpakstan Institute of Knowledge History, Archeology and Ethnography of the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan (1959) in the field of the study of archaeological monuments in the Usturt and Khorezm oases led to great discoveries and achievements in the research of medieval monuments [11].

In 1958-1960, under the guidance of Professor V. N. Yogadin, the head of the Department of Archeology of the Institute, he carried out systematic search research of the medieval monuments on the Right and Left banks of the Amudarya basin. These years, the researchers started from Havr castle fortress (Mizdakhon)

in Khojaly district, Munshaqli, Tuproq castle (Kongirot district), Tomir castle I- In the II-III, Bugrahon, Pulijoy, defensive fortifications were built in the middle ages (IX-X centuries) in the nomadic field zone, and then during the Khorezmshah period, the monuments that became trade and craft centers in the border areas were investigated [8. 228].

The results of the investigation proved that this is one of the monuments of the urban development culture located along the Usturt entrance system, one of the centers of the ancient and medieval agricultural culture in the northern part of the Khorezm state [9. 173].

Then, in the new research conducted by the employee of this institute, Doctor of History M.M. Mambetullayev, V. N. Yagodin and Candidate of Science Yu. P. Manilov in the 80-90s of the 20th century, in the Aybuyur micro-uas, in the Usturt mountains, the Middle and Middle Ars and the Khorezmshah period. Monuments were studied [4. 167].

Thus, during the study of history, the location, construction and defense of the villages and towns of the bordering Khorezim oasis of Usturt and the border archaeological monuments belonging to the ancient and middle ages on the right and left banks of the Amudarya are widely archeological [10. 73]. As a result of conducting research, new items were collected. On the basis of the analysis of the materials taken from the layers related to the history of the defense system of the ancient and medieval fortifications of the monuments, major fundamental works were created [7. 158].

The above-mentioned works of S.P. Tolstov contain general information about the memorial topographical structure and defense system of the ancient and early medieval cities of Usturt, and their role in the urban planning and defense system has been extensively studied archaeologically.

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